

Analysis of Electrooculogram in Detecting Eye Movements Associated with Brain Injury

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Abstract:

Electrooculogram (EOG) has been a valuable clinical neurophysiology tool in the past five decades of the twentieth century. It facilitated understanding more about eye movement, which is clinically useful in identifying the neural substrate disrupted due to brain injuries. This is vital since accurate measurement of neural injuries has a direct bearing on a patient's life. A number of neurological investigations, including neurological assessment and diagnosis, are done based on measuring eye movements. This essay focuses on using EOG technology and its benefits in identifying limitations of using physiological indices in individuals because of

measurable ocular pathophysiological parameters. In the current essay, the major objective will be to discuss the EOG features, the EOG record in healthy individuals, and the relationship of EOG recordings to affected individuals following a neurological event.

The eye-integrated EOG recorded from the front part of the face measures eye position change and shows an exponential decay of voltage due to its design, eye physiology, and the removal of corneal function slowly from the corneal electrode. This makes it the best choice to provide an eye position record with high accuracy that can be made available easily for clinicians. The rapid recordings obtained using transcranial electromagnetic stimulation could demonstrate that EOG has the potential to provide high pre-surgical planning utilities for brain tumor removal. This technology is also best for identifying physiological variability within an individual; the same concept can be extended to study brain injuries that trigger physiological changes in eye muscles. In effect, it potentially becomes a tool for personalized care wherein severity estimation for brain injuries would be based on measuring ocular function rather than the nature of the injury. Given its clinical potential, the present essay will review EOG technologies to assess eye pixel movement, its potential for clinical evaluation, physiological basis, and the research evidence regarding changes in EOG in affected individuals with brain injury. In this essay, the long-lasting and short-lasting EOG changes are presented as case studies of individuals diagnosed with PTA, hence demonstrating its clinical utility.

Keywords: *Electrooculogram, neural injuries, brain injury, assessment and diagnosis, personalized care tool.*

Introduction

Electrooculogram (EOG) literally refers to eye movement signals of electric nature and is made

up of two components, namely 'electro,' which is electrical, and 'oculogram,' which refers to the recording of ocular movements. The ocular

movements are actually synchronized movements of the eyes. The EOG signal is derived largely from the potential difference between the cornea and the retina, both being the positive and negative poles of the upper part of the electrical circuit surrounding the ocular structure. When the eyes move, the steady potential is disturbed first and then restored as the movement ends. That is to say, horizontal and vertical movements do cause alterations of the resting potential at the front of the eye because of the mechanical rotation of the eyeball.

To understand EOG, it is essential to keep in mind an ocular electric potential caused by the electric nature of the cornea and the retinal layers. This potential resides constantly and is built on a steady-state theory. In addition to the resting potential, the electric potential surrounding the eyes is also influenced by the membrane-separating ions ratio maintained by Na⁺ and K⁺ pumps and the permeability of the ocular cells. The electrooculographic vector provides both gaze tracking and control in communication devices, and its vertical component is also used in detecting sleep states. Alternating current, two-channel amplifiers, electrodes, differential amplifiers, band-pass filters, power line filters, and a notch filter are some EOG equipment. Calibration is a fundamental requirement in EOG measurement. All EOG equipment must be grounded and verified during the entire duration of recording. Signals that are continuous throughout the recording session are the best way to ensure undistorted EOG signals. In the absence of proper instrumentation for EOG recording, EOG signals may contain clipping artifacts and higher noise. There is also a relationship between EOG and certain movements of the eyes. EOG is used extensively in the diagnosis of varied diseases and conditions (Latifoğlu, İleri, & Demirci, 2020; İleri, Latifoğlu, & Demirci, 2022; Sciarrone, Bisio, & Garibotto, 2020).

Physiological Basis of Eye Movements

The process of eye movement is governed by numerous physiological phenomena critically interlinked with each other. When foveating a stationary target, our eyes perform small, rapid, jerky movements, termed saccades. These are subjected to intense voluntary control and thereby depend on the intention of the subject. The control of saccades is organized in such a manner that a short intention initiates a movement much before all the processes involved in the motor plan get executed. Saccadic eye movements are coordinated by neural mechanisms of the ocular motor plant, i.e., the brainstem, which is related mostly to horizontal saccades and extraocular eye muscles. These brainstem areas define the vector of a saccade; that is, direction, velocity, and amplitude.

The central nervous system integrates the efferent as well as the afferent pathways, including sensory information from the retina, and coordinates them in sync. Precise coordination of the motor components and processing of sensory inputs, such as head and body orientation, facilitate the end-effector movement to a specific location. The other types of eye movements are adaptive to visual and vestibular inputs and are termed smooth ocular pursuit. This compensates for the self-induced retinal slip occurring due to the tracking of a smoothly moving target. A few other types of slow eye movements known as the optokinetic reflex, vestibular ocular reflex, fixation, vergence saccades, and quick phases of nystagmus, have internal automatic mechanisms. Essentially, dynamic visual and vestibular information is used by the brain for the calibration and performance of these types of eye movements, which require precise coordination of saccades and smooth pursuit. Broken pathophysiological phenomena could be indicative of a group of symptoms in which the brainstem is injured. Hence, the knowledge of normal eye movements is of utmost importance as it can gauge the extent of brain injury using the advanced version of the above tests (Diaz-

Artiles, & Karmali, 2021; Wibble, Engström, & Pansell, 2020).

Anatomy and Function of Eye Muscles

The orbit of the eye consists of six muscles of diverse sizes and various orientations, which arise from the posterior aspect of the bony orbit and insert into the scleral coat of the eyeball. The lateral and medial recti abduct and adduct, respectively, and the superior and inferior recti elevate and depress the eye. The oblique muscles (superior and inferior) cause intorsion and extorsion, as well as abduction and adduction, in conjunction with the recti. In normal activity, the muscles are coordinated to prevent diplopia and conjointly converge and diverge as required for stereopsis.

Eye muscles, although apparently having different functions, do not necessarily focus their directions on a single point in space, but work together for harmonious movements. For example, during looking down, the superior and inferior recti coupled together act to depress one eye, but the two lateral recti should co-contract to pull both eyes to the midline to prevent exotropia. In addition, the superior obliques produce down intorsion, while the inferior obliques produce up extorsion to prevent an abnormal head tilt. The recti muscles give firm but not prolonged responses. Saccadic eye movements are especially dependent on the features of the partners that help in the prevention of overshoots, while tracking movements result from relatively slow contractions of the muscles. Interest in the dynamics of the partners in the distinct systems often comes from the need to estimate the strength of the linkages in the control model. The close neural link between the cerebrum, cerebellum, brain stem, and subconscious control through reticular formation using analogous motoneuronal systems dictates these characteristics of eye muscle functioning. Various types of diseases or traumas may affect the muscle system, resulting in eye movement abnormalities. Even drugs have an effect on the control system. The reliability and correctness of eye muscle practice are probable based on proprioception. Since muscles have a double

role in these reflexes, however, the afferent information should be predominantly from annulospiral nerves conveying rapidly altering activity (Greising, Corona, & Call, 2020; Lepley, et al., 2020; Lian, et al., 2022).

Types of Eye Movements

To interpret the ocular muscular changes, the eye movements are classified into various categories. These eye movements are recorded as EOG signals and help in diagnosing different neurological disorders. This is the reason why ocular movement is an integral part of computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging. Eye movements can be classified as saccadic eye movements, smooth pursuit, fixations, and vergence. Saccades are the rapid eye movements that shift the point of fixation from one place to another.

Saccades are the fast, jerky movements that allow the eyes to refixate onto different objects in the visual scene. The fixations are the periods of time in which the eyes remain stationary while visual information is collected. Smooth pursuit involves tracking a moving target while the image slips on the retina. A large system, including the frontal eye fields, superior colliculi, and the pontine reticular formation, is involved in the signal generation that induces all the saccades. The pursuits are controlled by neuronal activity in the posterior parietal cortex and the middle temporal visual area. The vergence eye movements are used to change the depth of the field. Briefly, we observed that different types of paradigms used in EOG signal processing can be utilized to monitor eye movements post-TBI damage (Laport, et al., 2021; Zhang, et al., 2023; Kastrati, et al., 2021).

Saccades

Saccade is one of the most important types of eye movements. It is characterized by simultaneous quick movements of both eyes in the same direction. Saccades are created through an interaction of an excitatory burst and an inhibitory burst of the agonists and antagonists of the superior rectus and inferior oblique/rectus muscles, which makes the eyes

turn to a new position abruptly. The burst cells are located in the Pontine Paramedian Reticular Formation, which is also responsible for initiating and controlling saccades. Vertical saccades are programmed using the superior colliculus. The neurophysiologic pathways for horizontal and vertical saccades are entirely separate, from the cortex down to the final nuclear/nerve innervation level. The corresponding eye muscles for horizontal saccades are the right and left lateral rectus and medial rectus, while the superior and inferior recti account for elevation and depression, i.e., vertical saccades.

Physiologically, the subcortical, frontal, and parietal cortices are responsible for the initiation and control of saccades in tandem with other parts of the brain. Normally, the eyes saccade about 2-4 times per second. These rapid and complex eye movements are important for visual scanning and information processing. Binding of the input from different complex saccades may form an image in the brain at a speed that is impossible to achieve through scanning the eyes. Evaluation with extreme precision of the spectrum of normal saccade properties may thus have the potential to reveal even minor abnormalities, which is beneficial in clinical medicine. Saccadic movements are studied using electrooculographic technology. A precise eye-movement registration is important to yield a precise diagnostic tool. Saccade studies can be used to gather information on patient populations with various neurologic diseases, including brain injuries. Emerging methods for quantification of normal saccades may also provide further targeted therapy in the longer term (Talanow, et al., 2020; Wolf, & Lappe, 2021; Schall, & Paré, 2021).

Brain Injury and Eye Movements

The Frankfurt Declaration has proposed a unified classification for adverse events in brain injury, including mTBI, sports concussion, and TBI. One characteristic shared by each of these neurological events is that the patients frequently present with visual symptoms, including diplopia and variation in visual acuity. Essentially, the

varied presentations of all kinds of brain injuries on eye movements happen with the initial treatment methods proposed according to symptomatological differences, and a number of additional diagnostics, including baseline testing, are irrespective of aetiologies and are involved with the impacts.

Brain injuries can be due to direct head trauma or non-traumatic causes. One problem across the field of diagnosing brain injury is that current imaging techniques are unable to detect mild to moderate brain injuries, and a normal scan does not clear the affected individuals from the potential consequences of a brain injury, as it can present itself as a late effect. In mild to moderate TBI, the damage to the brain at the time of the impact will alter some of the neurological activities, including the signal to the oculomotor nerve and affect the normal conjugate movement. Damage to cortical regions that store or absorb gaze memory or use the memory will present with patients having difficulty in performing simple tasks, requiring sustained focus or alternating between two simple tasks to become difficult. Disconnection of frontal, parietal, or temporal regions to the brainstem or in the thalamus will present as difficulty in executing a simple task (Tenovuo, et al., 2021; Meyfroidt, et al., 2022; Mondello, et al., 2021).

Concussion and Eye Movement Abnormalities

Introduction A concussion can disrupt the normal function of the eyes, as components of the thalamocortical pathways involved in eye movements can be affected. Though some post-injury eye movement abnormalities may not be immediately visualized, they may impair visual processing. Because of the potential visual symptoms that are common after a concussion, eye movement impairments can be evaluated using objective measures, including the electrooculogram, alongside other tests. Since a new section of the brain responsible for controlling eye movements is being explored, innovative rehabilitation strategies can be designed, especially if the injury affects its function. Hence, it is justifiable to include the assessment of eye movements as part of a

comprehensive concussion management protocol.

Saccades In at least one study, the production of reactive saccades was found to be different for individuals with concussions who needed to keep a "neutral neck" position before producing a saccade, demonstrating that the symptoms could affect saccade production. Therefore, changes in the direction or speed of saccades might be a sign of a concussion, though more research is needed.

Fixation The visuo-vestibular examination cannot only identify deficits in the relative functioning of the central structures processing ocular motor function, but also help with differential diagnosis, since some of the abnormalities cannot be visualized through standard clinical protocols.

Smooth Pursuit A cohort of athletes with concussions showed decreases in the gain of a smooth pursuit task relative to healthy controls in the acute, subacute, and chronic phases post-injury. Concentration, short-term memory, reproductive memory, the ability to think clearly, and emotional reactions are among the symptoms of mild concussions (Büttner et al., 2021; Uyeno, et al., 2022; Ding, & Lv, 2020)

Role of Electrooculogram in Brain Injury Assessment

Electrooculogram (EOG) is an eye movement recording technique that provides real-time data on any abnormality in the eye movement system. This recording technology holds promise in the diagnosis of brain injury and several neurological conditions such as dizziness, vertigo, headache, impairment of vision, and ear diseases, and permits insight into the recovery of eye movement. In contrast to the clinical evaluation of eye movement, which is confined to static (non-moving) and passive eye movements, EOG unlocks new dimensions for the evaluation of eye physiology. EOG is well-suited for real-world situations due to its ability to be utilized without additional equipment. It is especially useful in evaluating subtle disarrangement of saccadic and pursuit

movements. Fixation, saccades, pursuits, and optokinetics are considered promising parameters that can be evaluated through EOG for identifying disarrangement of the eye movement system.

The subjective evaluation of eye movements is often associated with large variability. The modern lynchpin of neurology should be a continuous objective evaluation of eye movements to overcome the obstacles of human variability, provide accurate diagnosis, and monitor the physiological improvements. With the advent of electronics, EOG acts as a reliable standalone tool that can be effectively used in everyday practice. The EOG technique is devoid of multiple problems caused by measurement techniques and is based on the visual domain capture of eye movements. Furthermore, EOG records eye movement during vision fixation, which makes it pertinent in clinical applications. As a result of advances in real-time monitoring of eye movements, EOG has become a powerful tool in neurology. EOG can be administered at any intervention point during acute, sub-acute, recovery, and chronic phases and across various etiologies. The neurology of tomorrow is the neurology of today with an objective tool of ocular motility analysis, namely EOG. With its lack of restriction, EOG is an open system tool for all practicing work from the emergency department to a tertiary care center. No restrictions. In the absence of verbal or non-verbal instructions, the elucidative role of EOG in complex medical conditions like brain injury blends with other equally relevant symptoms. The objective toolbox of EOG in brain injury is explained with pathophysiology and relevant case studies (Ding, & Lv, 2020; Farashi, 2021; Latifoğlu, Esas, & Demirci, 2020)

Advantages of EOG in Detecting Eye Movements

Electrooculogram (EOG) is a valuable tool to determine eye movement. Below, the characteristics of the EOG measurement as a tool to assess the status of the eyes are explained. EOG is non-invasive and contactless, so it can be conducted on head injury patients comfortably. Eye movement assessment by

EOG also does not make the patient experience dizziness, headaches, nausea, or vomiting, so the evaluation time for the patient is faster. The EOG measurement device is compact, lightweight, and its placement can be carried out in several different medical environments and conditions. EOG provides continuous monitoring of eye movement signals in real time for any changes. EOG is effective in discovering changes in eye movements with an accuracy of 1° by mapping eye movements from spontaneous quick phases to vestibulo-ocular reflex.

A broad application of EOG in clinical assessment allows for the estimation of neurological abnormalities related to the normal function of the eye (fixation and saccades); the effect of medication on the control of eye movement due to the central nervous system; visual tracking and performing saccade connections and slow phases; and the recovery of neurological injury. EOG, along with other neurodiagnostic tools, may be a single modality to focus on eye movement patterns and provide useful information to distinguish different types of brain injuries/diseases. In the measurement of EOG, there are also artifacts due to the movement of the eye and other organs, such as the flexor muscle and body movement. Although EOG sensors and amplifiers have developed a more sensitive model, the performance of tracking eye movements can still experience changes in the state of eye movement with a calm state. This change may be abnormal or indicate the presence of neurological damage in the brain or brain stem (Liu, et al., 2021; Nann, et al., 2020).

Methodology of Electrooculogram Recording

Electrical signals between the cornea and the retina produce a signal that can be monitored and analyzed to establish the direction of eye movement without the use of invasive techniques. In particular, the systems used rapidly sample the electrical activity of the eye and analyze the direction of movement. Although the systems of the early type relied on

a single monopolar corneal electrode with a remote reference electrode, it has been shown that this method is not as effective as using a bipolar corneal electrode. This new arrangement allows researchers and clinicians to record the difference in potential created when the eye moves, with the referential contact located near the orbit, while taking into account that the skin of the scalp acts as an uncontrolled remote reference electrode. In the standard electrooculogram recording, montages include the use of electrodes strategically placed near the location of the eyes. The placement of the corneal electrode is usually in either a bipolar or monopolar configuration, although different qualities of the EOG recording may be achieved with the use of contact-derived, equivalent, or three-opposite configurations. The configuration of the recording apparatus can also change depending on the studies. It is not uncommon for studies to take measurements in dark or bright lighting conditions, as well as use different tracking paradigms and different equipment for recording. Biological factors including individual differences, illumination intensity, and local anesthesia accompany the inherent EOG signals, while further affecting the basic tool of investigation. To collect EOG data with high sensitivity to subtle changes in eye position and gaze angles, it is vital to maintain a high estimation of internal and external validity, conduct original and inspiring approaches, and standardize calibration procedures. The application of the aforementioned methods explicitly influences signal enhancement, with the use of simple and non-specialist computing tools and advanced calibration methods contributing to providing promising and effective results for all researchers and clinicians (Pandiyani, et al., 2020; Lee, et al., 2020).

Electrode Placement and Configuration

As electrooculogram (EOG) tests eye movements from a distance, it is essential to ensure artifacts are minimized during any recording. This is best achieved through good preparation of the skin and proper configuration of the electrodes to maximize contact with the skin and improve the signal-to-noise ratio. Various techniques and configurations are

necessary to obtain the best quality recording possible for the type of eye movement you are recording. For the recording of horizontal eye movements using a limbal approach, the configuration would be different from that used for vertical saccadic recordings, which differ again from a systems approach where the corneoretinal potential is recorded. As both configurations differ depending upon the particular task, it may benefit the practitioner, at first, to record both recordings in the same recording session. The reason for this is that practically all EOG tests incorporate components of both vertical and horizontal eye movements.

Horizontal recordings: lateral eye movements are best performed with recording electrodes being placed into conjunctival fornices directly onto the limbus at the 3 and 9 o'clock positions, describing a circle around the cornea parallel to its surface. With the white sclera acting as the return electrode, no net corneoretinal potential is generated until the globe moves in the target direction. The EOG is bipolar and is normally seen as a deflection towards the active electrode (positive) and a mirror reverse at the inactive electrode. **Vertical recordings:** the subject should carefully position themselves in primary position for any vertical gaze shift and recorded from electrodes sagittally on the eye. Where possible, recordings were placed both above and below the eye. Positions advocated to record vertical saccades have varied slightly in the range of 30-60° above and 15° below the inferior lid margin. Owing to the difficulty of the latter placement and the likelihood of harder-to-interpret results owing to various factors, these sites are not generally recommended for clinical use. Where possible, data can be obtained from both the right and left eyes. It is crucial to clean the skin (but without abrasion) properly before placement. It is also crucial that the electrodes do not move from their optimum location over time. **Electrode preparation:** electrodes may be inserted directly into the conjunctival fornices or, more commonly, into a disposable supportive sheath. **Mitigating factors and troubleshooting:** always use gold or silver chloride electrodes. Be advised that any toxic

lens used will alter the extraocular muscle pulling vectors. The EOG, despite being a measure of potential differences over the cornea, will be contaminated by even the most trivial of head positional movements owing to the skin-based nature of it. Degradation of the trace may occur on lateral gaze observation on account of adverse scalp cap indication greater than 100 μ V. Special conducting gels are available for this purpose. The turning of the head or laying down on the contrary side should solve this potential recording artifact. Ensure the electrodes are not crimping the conjunctiva before attachment. The disposable covers for the electrodes are single use. Do not allow them to dry out after removal from the original package. Note the predictive recording differences on eliciting top gaze location on upward saccadic eye movements (Martino, et al., 2023; Amorim-de-Sousa, & Moreira, 2020).

Signal Processing Techniques for EOG Data

Electrooculogram (EOG) signals are subject to a number of noise and artifacts, the common ones being blink artifact, which is an effect of changes in the electrical potentials across the cornea and retina during eye blinks, and electrical interference from pulses due to movements. EOG data preprocessing is essential as part of the processing to remove blink artifacts, traces of saccades, and the trial-averaged waveforms. Data preprocessing in EOG data is primarily concentrated on removing signal artifacts and reducing noise incorporated in the recorded signal. One of the simplest and ideal methods is to reduce the presence of noise at the data acquisition setup stage. If there are systems that cannot be avoided, signal processing techniques are applied to ensure that data are accurate and correct. The EOG protocols will then have to be carefully and meticulously designed when dealing with clinical studies. Most applied works will consider large amplitude deviations from an engineering perspective. However, for clinical diagnosis of typical and mild injury, it is very difficult to interpret the eye movement patterns if an appropriate signal processing technique is

not utilized. These therapies thus enhance the original quality of the EOG data by employing various processing algorithms.

The filtered EOG signal is represented as $X(s)$. Data is not solely based on signal processing. Once the signals are filtered, the data mains would have to be rectified and smoothed to correct small gross changes induced in the signals. The resultant rectified signal, released from offset and normalized in percentage, is represented as $N(s)$. The PWM and pulse data samples are recorded through an oscilloscope. Filtered data samples for various eye movement patterns are presented in the research and signal processing software. Hence, baselining removes bias and reveals the trend in the data. All unprocessed raw EOG data were removed to clean the data by this processing technique. The Electrooculogram signal is heavily contaminated by baseline drift. Filtering techniques are devised to smooth the relationship between the EOG signal and time domain in order to minimize the presence of noise and correct artifacts in the data. Various algorithms used in the present study effectively reduce the presence of noise and improve the quality of the original EOG data. Based on this information, normalization was treated as user preference for the conversion of raw to clean data. No special signal processing tool was used for the major filtering of EOG data in the experimental work. Filtering and the removal of noise from an EOG signal, which typically identifies signals in particular frequency bands, are very well accepted. Hence, signal processing tools were employed to enhance the quality of the original EOG data. The bandpass frequencies for EOG saccades and EOG slow fluctuation are detailed (Mujeeb Rahman, 2024; Tian, & Cao, 2021).

Filtering and Artifact Removal

For further processing of EOG and in particular eye movement data, robust filtering is required to combat disturbances from corneal-retinal potential induced by saccadic eye movements. Such electrooculogram measurements, however, are generally distorted by several kinds of noise sources and artifacts, which have to be eliminated. The EOG signal is an electrical brain

signal and, as such, is especially influenced by physiological artifacts or noise, including noise contamination by muscle activity due to skeletal, heart, or eye muscles, and eye blinks or eye rolls, as well as environmental influences. Depending on the application, further physiological artifacts may originate from patient groups like those with epilepsy or eye problems. Even replicating the experimental setup and providing good instructions to the patient on how to wear electrodes might lead to reduced patient suffering; the artifact may arise due to disabilities or confusions of the patients.

There are two main steps to remove artifacts in biosignals. First, the testing step identifies when the data is contaminated with artifacts. Second, modifying the artifact-contaminated data minimizes new artifacts because of the data modification. The major problem in data modification is that false modifications might appear if the data quality assessment is not valid. Artifact detection is usually employed to check for the presence of noise or artifacts. As a result, some markers can be employed to evaluate the signal quality. It is highly recommended to visualize the signal and some statistics like histogram mean and standard deviation. In applying the filters, signal analysis always comes after filtering, but the filter-related results can be used to evaluate signal quality and discard bad data. Several applications use both statistics and visualization to measure signal quality. When analyzing biological signals, the requirements for signal quality detection differ based on the application's purpose. When applying the technique for an application, the signal or data used in the research must undergo the filtering and noise removal processes first. Research on the filtering and denoising methods requires valid statistics to assess filter performance. These statistics may include the mean and the standard deviation (Saba-Sadiya, et al., 2021; Gorjan, Gramann, & De Pauw, 2022).

Machine Learning Applications in EOG Analysis

In recent years, the increasing application of machine and deep learning has essentialized

workflows by enabling large-scale and automated analysis of distinct electrophysiological signals. After replicating diverse aspects of human vision and audition, researchers have directed algorithms to make rapid analysis and classification of electro- and magneto-physiological brain responses to naturalistic stimuli. In the context of analyzing saccadic-related gaze behaviors using saccadometry methods, machine learning techniques have been or could potentially be deployed to help in the following areas of EOG analysis: (1) automate and streamline event-related deflection recognition and categorization; (2) extract information from complex mixed multiple related saccade zones and patterns and then conduct automated qualitative interpretation of gaze findings; (3) reveal hidden correlations and complex multimodal patterns of saccadic activities that disclose a vast variety of conditions, such as disease sub-stages; (4) remove noise by harnessing the generalization power of some learning algorithms.

While such objectives are still far from being considered solved problems, the potential for machine learning utilities in EOG and, in general, saccadometry and oculomotricity studies deserves attention due to new potential scientific prospects. Overall, it is certain that integrating machine learning algorithms in EOG and saccadometry can bring both paced discovery and accelerated clinical diagnostic times — ensuring less subjective results (Hasan, Watling, & Larue, 2022; Min, et al., 2023).

Classification of Eye Movements using ML Algorithms

Many studies have explored the classification of eye movements through various machine learning methods when the signal originates from electrooculogram. The classification of saccadic and smooth pursuit movements is one of the most common methods in eye tracking. A range of different methods have been used for the analysis of EOG signals to classify different types of eye movements, including saccades, smooth pursuit, fixation, and others such as micro-saccades and rapid eye movements. The

accuracy of classification techniques is found to be significantly improved through effective feature extraction. Most features are selected on the basis of saccadic eye movements since they are the most significant and critical out of all eye movements. The widely used features generally describe saccade structure and characteristics such as amplitude, velocity, and acceleration. This also makes the classification accuracy for saccades the highest compared with other eye movements. Evidently, other types of features have been used to a lesser extent, such as entropy features and some frequency-related features.

Various performance metrics have been used to evaluate the classification accuracy for different machine learning models in a number of studies. These commonly include accuracies, confusion matrices, occurrences, sensitivity, and specificity. When eye movements that do not fit into the saccade and smooth pursuit classification occur, such as fixations and scanning, some studies subdivide them. Outcomes in different studies are inconsistent; while some studies found good performance, others reported results that suggest potential technical challenges. However, achieving good eye movement classification is highly pertinent to clinical environments since it can provide not only an eye movement database describing detailed strategies but also subtypes and timings such as micro-saccades. Furthermore, if machine learning can be suitably adapted to output and can learn continually over time from input data, it could greatly enhance the ability to constantly improve patient interaction with computers and allow for constant improvements in signal processing. This process will reduce errors significantly over time, eventually having the potential to significantly reduce the impact of mistakes on patient outcomes. This does not only include the reduction of error but also the development of a robust system that is highly accurate, so much so that it can be used for individualized diagnostics. For example, machine learning can be used to classify regular and irregular saccades, which are difficult to classify with default and standard systems.

In some studies, classification models with machine learning algorithms have been tested

and utilized in practice with relatively good results. Random forests, support vector machines, k-nearest neighbors, and others have been used to classify different eye movements. Generally, the performance of the method is found to be one of the factors influencing the classification accuracy across multiple studies. Other possible reasons could be misleading data sources such as abnormal baselines, although this problem is rather rare in such an unhealthy population, and unclear separation between classes. Data sources and models will be further explored to elicit explanations (Mao, et al., 2020; Vabalas, et al., 2020).

Clinical Studies and Findings

Over the years, several clinical studies have investigated the application of Eye-Chief-Agent Ratio (ECA-ratio), which is a measurement based on electrooculogram (EOG), as a tool for diagnosing relevant information concerning the degree of mild brain injury and in the course of recovery after brain injury. Data from these studies demonstrate a strong relationship between eye movements and vestibular symptoms. Selecting patients with mTBI for such clinical trials with a focus on the oculomotor system is largely based on this relationship. The selection of both included participants and outcome measurements differs between these studies. Outcome measurements consisted of the following: vestibular ocular reflex (VOR) parameters, ECA-ratio in response to a saccade, and/or in response to a head impulse.

All studies demonstrated an impaired ECA-ratio compared to healthy subjects. In one study, only the ECA-ratio of the saccade did not differ between patients with UVD and central pathologies (other than mTBI) and healthy control subjects, whereas the ECA-ratio in response to the head impulse did differ. The ECA-ratios of patients in one study—those were patients with posttraumatic complaints due to an accident resulting in an mTBI—correlated significantly with subjective clinical symptoms in response to a head impulse, such as patient

reports of dizziness and imbalance (Chen, Li, & Liu, 2023; Tsai, et al., 2021).

Studies on EOG in Traumatic Brain Injury

The analysis of EOG in traumatic brain injury (TBI) has intrigued researchers. A total of four studies have been conducted in TBI and reported a good correlation of oculomotor scores and EOG during trials. A study investigated the immediate, automatic task-related oculomotor performance in the post-acute stage of TBI. Another study evaluated the characteristics of the erroneous vestibulo-ocular reflex after TBI. A different study investigated if eye-gaze preclusion can be an outcome measure of a prospective control trial. Another study explored the characteristics of the saccade error time course following concussion. A total of 15 control participants were recruited in one study. Another study recruited a total of 54 healthy participants (18-68 years old). A single-center observational case-control study enrolled a total of 4 TBI participants and 13 control participants. Another study enrolled a total of 19 TBI participants to investigate the errors of the VOR. Today, EOG has been employed in some of the clinical trials along with other commonly used scales. Major structures and assessment tools used in TBI studies are listed in a table. Major findings of the EOG in TBI studies are summarized in another table.

The EOG has been used in TBI to help understand if the severity of the injury can be predicted. All these studies reported a good correlation of oculomotor EOG scores and direct clinical scales. They suggested that EOG can be used to prognosticate patients and guide clinicians in treatment. One study recommended the use of EOG alone to help with the recovery of ocular motor guidance to reduce the risk of falls after a concussion. The responses of participants in these studies were found to be highly variable. This might be due to a range of factors including the way brain injury was sustained, the loss of consciousness, and the subsequent brain loss following the injury. A range of factors can contribute to the variability. The EOG studies showed that typically TBI patients are able to fixate on a target after a

concussion. However, when actively moving their eyes, the EOG studies showed subtle differences between patients with concussion and healthy control participants. Consequently, more research is required to understand the subjective experience of patients who are able to direct their eye movements to the target but report ongoing symptoms or movement problems. More EOG studies are required in TBI undertaken by independent laboratories to confirm the results (Noor, et al., 2021; Kazazian, et al., 2021).

Challenges and Future Directions

Bridging Signal-to-Noise Ratio and Data Analysis Requirements to Applications: The foremost challenge inhibiting the widespread clinical acceptance or reliable use of EOG for brain injury assessment is the low signal-to-noise ratio inherent to the signals. Research in predictive filtering and signal loss compensation has achieved limited success. EOG is also subjected to interfering signals that mask the high-gamma signals. Additionally, the underlying anatomy differs between participants; for instance, the Cartesian coordinates are not always representative of the actual gaze position in space. Real-time systems additionally necessitate addressing technical issues such as detoxification, the risk of self-injury, and elements for communicative appliances, especially in the case of high head injury. Methods for recording are still not standardized, necessitating validation of the techniques employed.

Directionality of deflections cannot always be solely associated with saccades. Also, little is known about an injured brain's response to VS/VE in young adults. Many of the limitations can be overcome by employing sensor improvements or involving machine learning in data analysis. Accumulating evidence regarding the measure should not be generalizable to a variety of conditions or people, given short samples of patient data, small sample sizes, or young healthy individuals. Future directions in EOG-associated research would revolve around obtaining the highest diagnostic precision,

followed by selecting the optimal and defining the breadth of neurological conditions for which EOG could be potentially useful. The EOG signals have shown potential for applications in multiple clinical conditions; however, the use of EOG signals in specific studies and conditions has its unique challenges, benefits, and futures. Furthermore, EOG may have applications beyond brain injury and prognosis, such as the detection of neurological disorders. The interdisciplinary entities coming together from different fields will be essential to ensuring technological developments and methodological advancements are sufficiently able to make this diagnostic process a guide for the clinic, both now and in the future. Furthermore, further clinical trials will be essential in the validation of these empirical techniques.

Integration of EOG with other Brain Imaging Modalities

Despite the enormous promise of combining a range of different brain imaging techniques, much previous research has tended to isolate information from each, and the combined approach is very much an area still in its infancy. EOG, one such distinct modality, is able to measure overt eye movements in the identification of both the presence and absence of consciousness. EOG research is pertinent because it represents a clear separation between voluntary action and rest, and because the testing can take place autonomously of both clinical facilities and trained professionals.

EOG has been compared to other imaging techniques to demonstrate its relative efficacy, with the conclusion that EOG is not only markedly less expensive given its requirements, but it is comparable in many cases. For example, a study explored the similarities of data recorded from electroencephalogram (EEG), functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), and EOG, noting significant consistency in all but the signals recorded by fMRI. Using simultaneous EOG-fMRI, in which fMRI connectivity was informed by ocular sampling tasks, they could mine similar sources of information to infer networks associated with mental state correspondences. While fMRI and our ocular

technique were physically separable as a hybrid eye detection model from ocular features, the multivariate information embedded in occipital visual regions overlapped and could augment resting state networks.

Identifying the mechanisms of visual ocular motor control could offer a sensitive tool for clinical classifications related to different states of cognitive functioning, particularly in individuals with severe brain pathologies. Simultaneously or near-simultaneously recorded EOG and additional adjuvant techniques have been employed in recent research. For example, paired EOG-EEG recordings have been used to calculate information such as lateral magnetic motor evoked potentials, which may indicate the location of a lesion, and electrophysiological activity in particular cognitive visual processes. This method was combined with electroencephalogram recordings in order to investigate the relationship between electroencephalogram and electrooculogram oscillatory patterns. Applications such as these are instrumental for a multimodal approach to not only increasing the level of accuracy in diagnostics but also advancing understandings of the underlying mechanisms of brain functioning. Integrating these systems could thus be advanced to produce clinical prototyping.

Conclusion

In this study concluded that technology is also best for identifying physiological variability within an individual; the same concept can be extended to study brain injuries that trigger physiological changes in eye muscles. In effect, it potentially becomes a tool for personalized care wherein severity estimation for brain injuries would be based on measuring ocular function rather than the nature of the injury. Given its clinical potential, the present essay will review EOG technologies to assess eye pixel movement, its potential for clinical evaluation, physiological basis, and the research evidence regarding changes in EOG in affected individuals with brain injury. In this essay, the long-lasting and short-lasting EOG changes are

presented as case studies of individuals diagnosed with PTA, hence demonstrating its clinical utility.

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